

Gaps and Recommendations for Improving Technologies that Form the Data-to-Decision Pipeline

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A critical aspect of watershed intelligence is the utilization of various technologies to digitally link data to informed decision making. Here, we consider how technology contributes to watershed intelligence and what steps can be taken to improve the technology base for IWs. The technologies highlighted here were selected based on the frequency that they were mentioned by subject-matter experts during the first two phases of stakeholder engagement. The reviewed technologies are organized into three broad classes: data creation and collection; data management/informatics; and modeling and analytics.

1.1 DATA CREATION AND COLLECTION

Critical components of watershed systems relevant to hydropower can be summarized into several general categories (**Figure 1**). Data describing past and current conditions are collected using in situ sampling, ground-based observation networks, remote sensing instruments, and surveys or archival research. Other critical information is produced via models that estimate past, present, or projected conditions.

Figure 1. Informational categories relevant to hydropower at the watershed scale

Both observational and modeled information about facilities, their environment, and relationships to other natural and human systems are integral to evaluating the impacts and performance of hydropower systems. Across all data types and components, there must be consistency, accuracy, and adequate representation to be effective in describing relationships and driving decisions. The following section describes the current state-of-the-art for data collection techniques and products that are used in various hydropower decisions. For each category of data, there are several critical needs and recommended actions that can be taken to address current obstacles.

1.1.1 Water and Energy Users

Intelligent systems for hydropower must consider those who depend on and are impacted by water and energy systems as well as those who operate and make decisions about hydropower. Data derived from U.S. Census records describe key community demographics that are essential for understanding energy and water demands (i.e., high-density populations in residential areas have different resource demands than rural, low-density population agricultural communities). At a more granular level, information about communities includes public perception and interests related to specific hydropower projects, which can be critical to the success or failure of project relicensing or development or can be the catalyst for modifying operations. These data are typically collected through surveys and archival research methods and often require translation from qualitative to quantitative terms. Because of the benefits and burdens experienced by members of water and energy resource systems, all individuals or groups can be viewed as experts; if not technical experts in the policies or mechanisms of water, energy, or environmental systems, they have expert knowledge of their own participation within a system and of their own needs.

1.1.1.1 Gaps

Some critical challenges specific to data collection for water and energy users/communities are:

- **Sustained relationships and compensation for time, effort, and expertise:** Gathering data about any community requires investment in long-term relationships. This is especially true for tribes and communities where trust and partnership have seldom been historically built up or maintained beyond individual projects.
 - There are significant barriers to obtaining data when researchers, analysts, and decision makers are unfamiliar with or disconnected from relevant communities or social groups. Trust is needed to gain access to accurate information about those who are a part of the watershed system either as water/energy resource users or those who have interests that either complement or compete with hydropower objectives.
 - Community representatives and experts may have limited capacity to participate in collaborative efforts due to constraints on personnel and financial resources. These limitations are exacerbated when community experts are not compensated for their time and knowledge or when there are no plans for sustaining a relationship beyond the life of a project.
- **Inclusion in planning stages:** Social scientists, and experts in urban planning and human geography are critical members of water and energy planning studies and need to be integrated into discussions at the outset of projects, whether developing new infrastructure or changing existing operations. Failure to incorporate their perspectives could result in inaccurate or insufficient data.
- **Identifying representatives:** There are few resources beyond personal networks and word of mouth to help identify local organizations who are active in the communities influenced by hydropower projects.
- **Representation of values:** The social nexus with hydropower projects for communities near hydropower dams and reservoirs (e.g., recreational utilization) is poorly documented. These intersections include recreational utilization, cultural heritage and connections to the land and water, and general access to resources like water and land. There are also a variety of impacts on communities such as displacement or loss of livelihoods. Incomplete representation of different values and uses of the land, water, and energy contribute to the challenge of evaluating benefits and burdens of hydropower projects and operations.

1.1.1.2 Emerging Solutions

Mirroring the scale and national consistency of census data, several national datasets have been produced to describe socially relevant intersections with water, environmental, and energy systems. One example is the USGS [National Water Use Information Program](#), which has provided ongoing updates with a frequency of 5 years and resolution of water use by sector. The representation of different end uses is critical to understanding variation in priorities and behavior throughout the country.

In addition to water demand data, there are also a variety of efforts to regularly gauge attitudes about climate and natural resource management. Although these data largely describe historical conditions or provide snapshots of current conditions, as they are maintained and updated, they help describe how the human aspect of water and energy systems have evolved and how different values, perceptions, and behaviors of various communities throughout the US can influence water systems.

1.1.1.3 Recommendations

Implement Technical Assistance Programs

- Technical assistance (TA) programs have largely focused on lab-federal agency partnerships. However, TA programs for tribes, community organizations, etc., could be used to more formally structure and build sustained relationships with those gathering information on resource use and community values.
- These types of programs can facilitate more organic and efficient data collection about community groups because those with existing relationships and knowledge of communities are already playing a central role in the project.

Bridge technical and social sciences

- Training and workforce development are needed to work effectively with community groups, and gather/integrate social data.
- Funding and support for research/technical staff to attend regional conferences will help build and maintain connections with key gatekeepers of knowledge about specific communities or social groups.

Incorporate existing tribal data and traditional knowledge

- Some crucial information about the values and use of water and energy resources are likely to be maintained at the tribal or regional level.
- Traditional knowledge may be foundational to understanding the socio-environmental history of any particular location that goes beyond current monitoring and record keeping practices.

Develop forward-looking water and energy demand data

- Trends and historical use of water and energy may not hold into the future; shifts in public attitudes/behavior towards certain technologies and growth in new industries can disrupt existing systems.
- Accurate projections of water and energy requirements rely on representations of population growth, community behavior, and attitudes towards different development and resource consumption practices.

Index community-oriented information to key boundaries and features

- Geospatial links between important community descriptors and relevant hydrologic or infrastructure systems will facilitate analyses at scales that are more meaningful to hydropower and watershed-scale interests (instead of geopolitical boundaries such as census tracts or counties, which are typical of social data). Examples of relevant systems that could be referenced include the 3D National Hydrography Program, water or energy service boundaries¹, or hydropower complex project boundaries.
- Harness crowd-sourced data, that can describe use and value of water and energy resources. Novel forms of publicly available data include visits (e.g., frequency or unique check-ins) or reviews of recreational sites.
- Geospatial data describing the local organizations that are active in certain areas can help in connecting with experts on specific community interests.

1.1.2 Streamflow

Streamflow is one of the most important environmentally sensed measures for watershed management. Streamflow data inform real-time river operations, are foundational to river forecasting, and are among the most important variables for calibrating water-resource models. Traditionally, streamflow or discharge is estimated from measured water levels using a site-specific stage-discharge rating curve developed from onsite water level and streamflow measurements (Turnipseed & Sauer, 2010). The United States Geological Survey (USGS) maintains an extensive network of over 8,500 gauges across the U.S. (there are an additional 1,700 sites that only measure water level) with the data available online in real and near real-time². While the stream gauges are primarily operated and maintained by the USGS, most are funded in partnership with a wide range of organizations that rely on these gauges to manage river operations. Flow measurement has been recently augmented with real-time imagery at over 850 locations across the U.S.³ These images are used internally by USGS staff to aide in water level, streamflow, and water quality data analysis and approval and provides valuable remote situational awareness of site conditions that is publicly available. The USGS is developing and evaluating new methods to use imagery data as inputs to models to derive streamflow and other parameters, but these are not yet operational.

1.1.2.1 Gaps

While the U.S. streamflow gauging systems are among the best in the world, remaining obstacles and gaps impact water management:

- **Coverage.** The most common issue voiced by stakeholders was that there are just not enough gauges, especially in certain types of systems. In particular, monitoring in small watersheds is underrepresented, and there are few paired gauges upstream and downstream of reservoirs. Remote and inaccessible locales also represent a problem for stream gauging.
- **Inconsistency.** Other challenges include differences in how measurements are made (i.e., different sensing technologies), differences in measurement frequency, and frequent misalignment in space and time between streamflow data and other relevant measurements (e.g., water quality data may be collected in a different location than stream flow). Nearly one-quarter of current active gauging stations provide only water level (USGS, 2024); without accurate rating curves, these values cannot be translated to streamflow.
- **Sustained operations.** A key challenge with stream gauging is related to the cost to establish, maintain, and operate the gauges. Regionality, different types of measurements and alert systems, and site-specific installation challenges result in varied costs for gauging systems. For example, current first-year O&M costs for stage-only gauges are \$28,000 (subsequent cost is \$6,000/yr), while stage-discharge gauges cost \$36,500 for first-year O&M and \$14,500/yr subsequently (J. Woods and P. Cinotto, personal communication, March 13, 2025). The issue of long-term funding was recently reviewed by the Congressional Research Service (Normand, 2021). Recent analysis of USGS streamflow gauges indicate roughly 1,300 (27%) of eligible locations for Federal Priority Streamgauges are inactive due to current lack of funding (USGS, 2024).

¹ An interview of the Internet of Water by Environmental Policy Innovation Center discusses the importance of recent efforts to create a national map of water utility service boundaries and include drinking water metrics in datasets describing communities: <https://www.policyinnovation.org/blog/service-area-boundaries-j40-case-study>

² Additional information about the national gauge network and historical and real-time data can be downloaded from the USGS National Water Information System data portal: <https://waterdata.usgs.gov/nwis>

³ Additional details on the USGS Hydrologic Imagery Visualization and Information System can be found on the HIVIS website: <https://apps.usgs.gov/hivis/>

1.1.2.2 Emerging Solutions

Advances in flow-measurement technologies are being pursued on a variety of fronts. These include noncontact techniques such as ultrasonic or radar measurements to estimate river stage and flow velocity at reduced cost (Costa et al., 2006). Alternatively, remote-sensing approaches using cameras (Tauro et al., 2017), uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) (Bandini et al., 2021), and satellites (Durand et al., 2023; Moramarco et al., 2019) provide a whole new way of measurement. However, satellite-based approaches are unable to detect smaller water systems. Artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) are increasingly used to translate remotely sensed information into discharge estimates (Mukherjee et al., 2023; Vanden Boomen et al., 2021). Inexpensive sensors are increasingly being tested and deployed, though these may have tradeoffs with data security and reliability.

In 2018, the USGS initiated the Next Generation Water Observing System ([NGWOS](#)) that integrates fixed and mobile sensors to provide increased spatiotemporal coverage of water in different forms, i.e., streamflow, snowpack, evapotranspiration, groundwater, etc. Importantly, streamflow data are collected and shared alongside other key measures including water quality and water usage, which supports water prediction, decision support, and hazard response systems. To date, five such networks have been established that provide incubators for water-observing instrumentation (**Figure 2**). Other intensive monitoring networks that include dense stream gauges are the [DOE Watershed Science Focus Areas \(SFAs\)](#). Some of the ongoing SFAs are located in critical regions for hydropower, including the headwaters of the Upper Colorado River Basin (Watershed Function SFA), portions of the Tennessee River Basin (Watershed Dynamics and Evolution SFA), and Yakima River Basin (River Corridor Hydrobiogeochemistry SFA). However, connections to hydropower systems are not specific priorities of these programs.

Figure 2. Overlay of existing conventional hydropower capacity with locations of major monitoring testbeds. These include Department of Energy-supported field laboratory and Watershed Science Focus Areas (SFA) sites and the current basins supported through the USGS Next Generation Water Observing System (NGWOS) program.

1.1.2.3 Recommendations

Leverage remote sensing and AI/ML together

- Cameras, multi- and hyper-spectral sensors on remote sensing instruments are able to retrieve information with unprecedented spatial and temporal coverage. Continued investment in AI/ML technologies can help harvest and interpret information from remotely sensed data. For example, AI/ML can be coupled with remotely sensed altimetry to interpret changes in river or reservoir elevation and estimate discharge from reservoirs. As coupled applications are sustained, they can be used for sustained and consistent creation of long-term records.

Extend monitoring testbeds to hydropower watersheds

- Apply multi-instrument monitoring techniques used in NGWOS and DOE Watershed Science Focus Areas, with an applied perspective. For example, performance of cameras and remote sensing techniques should be examined at different points within hydropower systems.

Ensure new stream gauge siting addresses hydropower objectives

- Identify critical locations within river systems that are relevant to hydropower operations but are currently insufficiently supported by the existing stream gauge network. While water forecasting and federal reservoir operations are called out as strategic priorities and responsibilities of recent re-designs of the Federal Priority Streamgauge program, there is no explicit emphasis on using stream gauges to support hydropower decisions.
- Examples of critical additions include:
 - temporary installation of stream gauges upstream of non-powered dams to better measure water availability for future development/retrofit of dams
 - gauging new sites in basins with rapidly changing land cover or development.

1.1.3 Snowpack

Snowpack is a critical source of natural water storage in mountainous terrain and northern latitudes during the winter months. Estimation of the stored snow water equivalent (SWE) and related melt dynamics is critical to forecasting streamflow, water supplies, and potential for springtime flooding. Estimation of snow coverage, snow depth, and SWE rely on a range of monitoring technologies including a comprehensive network of manually measured snow courses, aurally monitored snow gauges, automated precipitation gauges, and Snow Telemetry (SNOTEL) monitoring sites. These sites are largely managed by the Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) in the western U.S. and nationwide by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) National Snow and Ice Data Center. These ground-based measurements are augmented by a variety of remote-sensing technologies that provide indirect measures of snowpack at low spatial and temporal resolution but over large regions. These technologies include the Land Data Assimilation System (National Aeronautics and Space Administration's (NASA) Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL)) and the SNOW Data Assimilation System (NOAA), which use sophisticated numerical models of physical processes to integrate data from multiple ground and space-based observing systems in order to produce gridded snowpack and SWE estimates across the U.S.

1.1.3.1 Gaps

While significant advancements have been achieved with snowpack monitoring over the last few decades, many opportunities remain for improvement. Among the greatest challenges are:

- **Limitations of ground-based snowpack networks.** Field monitoring of snowpack is critical for ground-truthing remote monitoring methods and calibrating models. Manual collection of variables describing snow are often collected along with other variables at meteorological stations. While data may be accurate at these locations, there are major limitations in the spatial density that makes ground-based surveys largely unsuitable for basin-scale applications (Dong, 2018). Additionally, many ground-based sensors rely on the use of empirical calibration equations that may not be valid at all geographic locations.
- **Uncertainty of remotely sensed data at fine resolutions.** While remote sensing provides substantially greater spatial coverage than ground-based measurements, remote sensing data suffer uncertainty in estimating snowpack properties at spatial and temporal scales by which they vary. The most widely used remote-sensing products are passive microwave sensors, which are not only affected by the snow mass (snow depth and density) but also by structural parameters, such as snow layering, microstructure, temperature, and moisture. These sensors typically have resolutions ranging from 250-500m. Advances in active sensors are reaching higher resolutions of 10-100m for some snow parameters such as SWE and snow depth (Shrestha & Barros, 2025).
- **Challenges with converting measurements to snowpack estimates.** High-resolution snow evolution models are necessary to capture important snow consolidation and melt dynamics, heterogeneities, and interactions between snow and land cover, allowing for improved snowpack estimates. These models suffer from a lack of continuous and reliable weather forcing data sets and accurate rendering of critical physical processes at tractable scales (Merkouriadi et al., 2021).

1.1.3.2 Emerging Solutions

Laser altimetry using Light Detection and Ranging (Lidar) is finding greater application in snowpack monitoring given its good sensitivity and high spatial resolution (decimeter-scale accuracy and meter point spacing). Lidar is generally deployed as an airborne-sensing technology requiring small aircraft or a UAV. One of the largest impediments to its broader application is the high cost of the necessary equipment coupled with required operator training.

Several detailed testbed experiments are being supported by a range of federal agencies to better connect ground-based measurements, remotely sensed information, and physical modeling to better forecast snow dynamics. NASA's [SnowEx](#) program is a multi-year field experiment, which includes extensive surface-based observations to evaluate how to best combine different remote-sensing technologies to accurately observe snow throughout the season in various landscapes (e.g., forest, mountain, prairie). Different testbeds consider the wind, precipitation, and temperature regimes these snow covers evolve within, and that snow depth, density, number of layers, grain characteristics, metamorphic trajectories, and melt sequences differ across these various landscapes. Some of the testbeds introduced in Section 1.1.2 *Streamflow* (USGS NGWOS basins, the East River SFA) and the Surface Atmosphere Integrated Field Laboratory ([SAIL](#)) include high-density, ground-based sensing systems combined with remote sensing and modeling to describe a full array of hydrologic processes including snow dynamics. These programs are aimed at addressing measurement challenges and exploring the fundamental physics that govern processes from snow fall to streamflow.

1.1.3.3 Recommendations

Improve the adoption of snow-related data for hydropower forecasting

- Determine needs for snow-related data from the hydropower industry. Engage hydropower owners/operators to establish forecast needs in to snow-dominated watershed systems.
- Quantify the costs and impacts of limited snow data on seasonal planning for multi-purpose reservoir storage and hydropower operations.

Improved automation

- Where in situ data for snow is particularly difficult to collect, there is significant need for improved automation of snowpack measurement instrumentation and sensors used in ground-based measurements.
- Similarly, automated retrieval of remote sensing products may enhance the spatial record of snowpack, especially in remote areas. However, the ability to accurately determine snowpack characteristics requires continued research investment, particularly when there are complicating factors (e.g., dust and particulate matter on snow).

1.1.4 Groundwater

Groundwater is a crucial piece of the puzzle budgeting and allocating uses and availability at the watershed scale. The topic of groundwater also includes near surface conditions in both the vadose zone and critical zone where interaction with roots and surface water take place. Vertical and longitudinal movement of water below the surface adds an additional layer of complexity to watershed-scale systems.

1.1.4.1 Gaps

Several challenges associated with observing or estimating groundwater include:

- **Extent of groundwater processes and access to monitoring sites.** Many wells on private lands are not regularly monitored or are even exempt from reporting. This poses a major challenge, since the aquifers contributing to the consumption of groundwater from a given well may extend far beyond the private property boundaries. Furthermore, interactions from deep and shallow aquifers can occur on vastly different time scales than is typically seen in surface water systems, with recharge being calculated in terms of years as opposed to seasonal, daily, or even sub-hourly surface water runoff.
- **Coverage and sustained operation of monitoring networks.** Similar to gaps noted in Section 3.1.2 for creation and collection of streamflow data, the ability of current groundwater data monitoring networks to represent large-scale processes with high resolution is limited by relatively sparse monitoring locations.

1.1.4.2 Emerging Solutions

Remote sensing records produced by satellites such as NASA's GRACE mission, which can provide estimates of how much water is stored underground by measuring changes in gravity. With a record building on more than one decade of observations, histories of groundwater depletion and recharge from

the GRACE mission have even been integrated with field measurements to downscale and provide estimates of groundwater quantities at roughly 5km scale (Agarwal et al., 2023). This may help approximate conditions more accurately for smaller watersheds in the future.

1.1.4.3 Recommendations

Integrate and compare field measurements, models, and remotely sensed estimates of groundwater

- Incorporating ground-truthed observations with coarse remotely sensed estimates will improve downscaled, higher resolution data that are relevant, especially at smaller watershed scales.
- Comparisons and demonstration of accuracy of remotely sensed estimates of groundwater will increase trust and adoption of remotely sensed estimates that can cover large areas that extend beyond individual watersheds.

Recognize importance of groundwater in water budgeting

- As an integral part of the water budget equation, groundwater must be accurately estimated or the whole estimate of available water and consumed water will not reflect real conditions.
- In many water management cases, the subsurface processes are not a primary or necessary interest to a decision. In these cases, it may be more important to track the net use of water, rather than then attempting to represent the interactions and different time scales at which the groundwater system is represented in the water budget.

1.1.5 Weather and Climate

Weather and climate⁴ data are vital for hydropower decision-making as these data inform water availability, flow variability, and the timing of peak runoff. Long-term climate projections help in planning for changes in precipitation patterns, snowmelt timing, runoff availability, and drought risks, which directly affect reservoir levels and energy-production capacity. On a day-to-day basis, accurate weather forecasting data enables operators to optimize water releases to manage flood risks and balance energy generation with downstream ecological needs. Extreme hydrological events such as floods or prolonged dry periods can significantly alter operations, and having reliable climate forecasts allows for proactive management to reduce risks to infrastructure and ensure consistent power generation.

1.1.5.1 Gaps

Obstacles in weather and climate data creation or collection include:

- **Resolution and accuracy of long-term climate projections.** While global climate models (GCMs) provide physics-based projections of future climate conditions, their outputs are typically coarse, with spatial resolutions around 100 km, and they may exhibit significant model bias. For hydropower systems and watershed scales, downscaling and bias-correction methods are essential to ensure that climate variables are represented at a more meaningful resolution. Local conditions—particularly in hydropower systems and watersheds with highly variable terrain, land

⁴ The distinction between weather and climate is outlined by NOAA where “weather reflects short-term conditions of the atmosphere while climate is the average daily weather for an extended period of time at a certain location.” For more information, see: https://oceanservice.noaa.gov/facts/weather_climate.html

cover, or dense populations—are not always captured, and finer representation would enhance the accuracy of future climate projections, ultimately supporting long-term forecasting and planning.

- **Complexity of working with model and scenario ensembles.** Modeled climate data are often produced as ensembles, representing different model assumptions and scenarios. Sparse descriptions of differences in underlying model setup or assumptions can lead to confusion or misinterpretations of projected climate data.
- **Differences and limitations among Meteorological Networks (Mesonets).** Mesonets or “mesoscale networks” of coordinated weather stations, have been established independently, largely on a state-by-state basis in the U.S., over the last several decades. There are approximately 27 state-supported mesonets with roughly 1,600 real-time weather stations⁵. Much of the guidance for placement centered around avoiding obstacles and approximating an “ideal” landscape—a flat, grassy surface in an undeveloped area with unimpeded airflow (Fiebrich et al., 2020). Because of this emphasis, mesonets do not typically represent conditions near dams or reservoirs.
- **Harsh and remote environments.** The ability to collect continuous meteorological measurements in a variety of environments is critical, but specific locations can pose a challenge for sensor deployment and maintenance. Sensor systems in more remote settings can be subject to malfunctions or interruption of data collection. Maintenance and upgrades are especially needed as weather observing networks age and sensor technologies advance (WSWC, 2024).

1.1.5.2 Emerging Solutions

To address the limited spatial and temporal coverage of weather stations and their historical records, significant efforts have been made to develop gridded meteorological datasets to support hydrologic model simulation. For example, the Analysis Of Record for Calibration (AORC; (Fall et al., 2023)) provides a state-of-the-art, hourly dataset of near-surface weather conditions covering the continental U.S. from 1979 to present, with spatial resolutions of 1 km and 4 km. Similarly, Daymet (Thornton et al., 2021) offers high-resolution, daily meteorological data for North America from 1980 to present. Another widely used dataset, Parameter-elevation Regressions on Independent Slopes Model (PRISM), delivers daily historical meteorological for the U.S. (Daly et al., 2008). However, inconsistencies exist among these datasets due to trade-offs between spatial and temporal resolutions, as well as coverage and interpolation procedures. These trade-offs must be carefully evaluated based on a watershed’s location, size, and the intended application of the data (Shuai et al., 2022). Some new efforts such as CONUS404 leverage high-resolution, numerical weather simulations to produce reanalysis datasets with 15-minute to daily temporal resolutions at a 4 km spatial scale (Rasmussen et al., 2023).

The above weather and climate data sources do not provide estimates of actual evapotranspiration (ET); PRISM includes potential ET, which does not reflect actual water content from the land surface. OpenET, an online platform providing estimates of actual ET at the field scale calls high-resolution ET “the biggest data gap in water management.”⁶ Remote-sensing data have long been used to estimate key parameters used in the energy and water balance of a watershed (Zhang et al., 2016), and programs like OpenET are leveraging historical and real-time remote sensing data to produce estimates of ET.

High-density and multi-parameter sensing networks focused on climate data, like the NGWOS networks described in Section 1.1.2 *Streamflow*, have been established and supported by DOE’s Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) user facility. In the testbed of the Upper Colorado Basin, the SAIL

⁵ In-depth descriptions of individual Mesonets and the evolution of weather measurement networks can be found via Campbell Scientific’s website on Mesonet Essentials: <https://www.campbellsci.com/mesonets>

⁶ See OpenET’s About Us and FAQ pages for in-depth discussion of the challenges related to observing and describing ET: <https://etdata.org/>

program⁷ explores measurement challenges and the fundamental physics of snow fall to streamflow. The ARM mobile measurement facility monitors precipitation, clouds, aerosols, wind, radiation, temperature, and humidity using more than four dozen instruments. The integration of this climate data and an “atmosphere to bedrock” perspective is motivated by providing data to inform forecasts of mountain hydrology.

To refine spatial resolution and address biases in GCMs, active research focuses on exploring suitable downscaling and bias-correction approaches to improve raw GCM projections. Generally, researchers employ two main approaches: dynamical downscaling, which uses regional climate models with GCM projections as boundary conditions, and statistical downscaling, which applies statistical techniques grounded in long-term, reliable historical meteorological observations. To avoid reliance on a single model or method, multi-model ensemble approaches have been adopted to better address uncertainties (Rastogi et al., 2022). Additionally, recent advancements have explored ML algorithms to efficiently generate downscaled climate projections, combining the strengths of both dynamical and statistical techniques. Despite these innovations, the hydropower community remains largely unfamiliar with these new products and resources. There is significant opportunity to support hydropower stakeholders in examining, visualizing, and leveraging these datasets to enhance long-term resource planning.

Other emerging solutions to help deal with the complexity of climate scenario and model ensembles are visualization and analytics platforms such as the [USGS National Climate Change Viewer \(NCCV\)](#). The NCCV aids in interpreting modeled climate data by describing projected changes at state, county, and hydrologic unit levels as well as providing useful summaries and statistics. These include climographs (monthly statistics for climate variables produced by different scenarios and models) and measures of regional agreement across different Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and GCMs.

⁷ Surface Atmosphere Integrated Field Laboratory Program: <https://sail.lbl.gov/about/>

1.1.5.3 Recommendations

1.3.2.2

Validate ET estimates in diverse watersheds

- While the focus for ET has historically been on agricultural applications and the western U.S., validation of ET estimates against ground-truthed data from diverse watersheds would help improve accuracy and build trust in ET data.
- Additionally, ET estimates at fine scales (i.e., daily) are not nearly as accurate as at coarser time intervals, which limits how this information can be used for water-management decisions.

Promote the adoption of ensemble-based, bias-corrected climate projection datasets to enhance long-term resource planning

- Traditional, long-term resource planning has often relied on historical observations, which may not represent a climate period reflective of future conditions. To better account for various sources of risk, it is essential to support efforts in the creation, validation, and integration of ensemble-based, bias-corrected future climate projections. These datasets can inform long-term resource planning by providing insights into projected future water availability.
- Ensemble-based projections may also highlight potential changes in future hydroclimate extremes, including both floods and droughts. Improving descriptions of underlying models and scenarios and exploration of the drivers behind differences in extreme behavior across model and scenario ensembles will improve the interpretation and adoption of more complex climate data. Specifically for extremes, the use of climate scenario and model ensembles will open the door for more comprehensive and robust planning and decision-making. See the emerging solution for visualizing climate ensemble data for water management purposes in Section 3.3.2.2.

Enhance the understanding and communication of regional and local weather forecasting capabilities

- Assess the historical accuracy of regional and local weather forecasts through rigorous validation analyses. For example, evaluate whether significant storms and extreme weather events were accurately predicted or if dam operators were caught off guard. This assessment can identify potential gaps in forecasting capabilities and inform improvements for better preparedness and decision making.

1.1.6 Water Quality

Under the general umbrella of water quality, there may be information reflecting the biological, physical, and chemical conditions of aquatic systems (both surface water and groundwater). Water quality data may be collected for general site monitoring, or in response to specific regulatory and compliance concerns (e.g., to evaluate whether a waterbody should be designated as impaired, to determine if water dischargers/permit holders are impacting environmental conditions, etc.). Most water quality data are collected in situ by collecting samples or with sensors; however, some parameters can be measured or approximated using remote-sensing techniques (satellites, UAVs). With respect to hydropower interests in a watershed, water quality data are typically collected to evaluate impacts of system operations and understand conditions that are relevant to ecosystem health (i.e., ability to provide adequate habitat for fish and other aquatic organisms) and human health (i.e., providing safe drinking water and recreational opportunities).

1.1.6.1 Gaps

- **Inconsistency across measurements.** There is a broad range of data needs and different measurement/monitoring techniques for various water-quality parameters, and each monitoring entity (e.g., state or federal agency) often has different measurement protocols. Additionally, as monitoring methods evolve, this can pose a challenge to assembling long-term records that are consistent. For example, more frequent observation of a water-quality impairment could reflect degradation in water quality, or it could be an artifact of the sampling schedule.
- **Limitations of sensing networks and manual data collection.** Water quality data are especially lacking in small watersheds. The cost of water-quality sensors can be prohibitive, especially if monitoring multiple locations within a reservoir/watershed. In situ data are often collected during limited times of the year or at infrequent intervals, resulting in temporally sparse and irregular data that may not match needs for analysis of temporal patterns or model development. There are also discrepancies in the level of detail and coverage of data collected at the surface vs. within the water column.
- **Gaps in remote-sensing data.** Remote-sensing data hold promise, but several uncertainties (i.e., linkages between spectral data and ground-truth, water-quality data) and data gaps (i.e., frequency of imagery acquisition, cloud obstructions) limit the ability to consistently detect water quality parameters with complete coverage.
- **Limited resources result in failure to identify impairments.** Particularly in communities who have not historically had sufficient representation or priority for monitoring, historical impairments may have gone unnoticed, contributing to inequitable monitoring and failure to document or track conditions in various communities. State agencies are required by the EPA to inform and engage with the public during continuing planning processes for monitoring and identifying impairments (e.g., holding outreach events and soliciting public comment). The EPA suggests the public could be involved by providing data, commenting on proposed plans, or working with third parties to conduct additional studies.⁸

1.1.6.2 Emerging Solutions

Several key advancements in water-quality monitoring come from the development of low-cost sensors and sensor-equipped drones. Uncrewed aerial, surface, and underwater vehicles that can collect data rapidly and in difficult-to-access environments offer significant improvements to the spatial coverage of typical field sampling. Conversely, instruments mounted on stationary buoys offer opportunities to collect

⁸ Guidance on the public role in the water quality impairment identification process is provided by the EPA: <https://www.epa.gov/tmdl/public-participation-listing-impaired-waters-and-tmdl-process>

continuous information within waterbodies at a high frequency and over long periods of time. In marine environments, the USGS has outfitted federally-operated or leased vessels with continuous monitoring equipment⁹. Similar mounting of recreational and commercial vessels in inland waters may help fill spatial and temporal gaps in traditional field data collection.

A notable testbed initiative is the [National Ecological Observatory Network \(NEON\) monitoring network](#), which features intensive sensor deployment in several watersheds. Eighty-one, long-term monitoring sites have been established across the U.S., with 34 of these as aquatic sites (streams, rivers, lakes). Almost all aquatic sites are co-located near terrestrial sites, to facilitate the ability to determine interactions and processes connecting terrestrial and aquatic environments.

⁹ USGS article on the Federal Oceanographic Fleet: <https://www.usgs.gov/programs/cmhrp/news/traversing-sea-science-how-usgs-uses-federal-fleet-study-natural-hazards>

1.1.6.3 Recommendations:

Identify strategic sites for data collection

- Similar to the recommendation for improving streamflow and other sensing-network densities, analysis of locations within hydropower watersheds or locations that are chronically under-sampled could help identify specific sites for prioritized water-quality monitoring. Possible priorities include:
 - Identifying rivers or reservoirs experiencing a confluence of issues that are exacerbating water quality conditions and merit additional focus.
 - Co-locating measurements of multiple variables can greatly increase system understanding and facilitate model development. Selection of new locations may take into account community or volunteer measurements that can complement measurements collected by professional scientists.
 - Determining the time scale most necessary for data collection that responds to particular hydropower objectives. Is monitoring needed for understanding impacts for a specific event, to establish an understanding of long-term or baseline conditions?
 - Augmenting state agency efforts to characterize surface water conditions in hydropower watersheds. Improved water quality data collection design could help at the local level by targetting areas that have been historically left out of regular monitoring plans.

Support experimental watershed case studies

- Site-specific and watershed-scale observational studies (e.g., DOE SFAs, NEON) and sensing networks (e.g., NGWOS) have greatly improved understanding of watershed systems and water-quality issues. However, watershed studies are most often conducted in less-impacted (e.g., forested), non-regulated systems.
- Active participation in technical working groups can influence how future data collection design and implementation could respond more directly to water and environmental objectives.

Prioritize in-situ measurements that facilitate ground-truthing of remotely sensed data

- Remote sensing holds promise for increasing spatial and temporal resolution of some water quality parameters such as water clarity and productivity. In-situ data collection in reservoirs that can facilitate the development/evaluation of remote-sensing algorithms should be prioritized.

Measure water quality conditions in relation to human health concerns

- Tracking conditions and identifying issues that pose a risk to human health requires frequent and sustained monitoring of a suite of parameters. Greater coverage and strategic siting of regular water quality monitoring sensors or data collection may support increased access to clean water and avoiding exposure to conditions that are pose a risk to health such as toxic algal blooms.

1.1.7 Water and Energy Infrastructure

The physical infrastructure of a hydropower system, including dams, power plants, and transmission lines, is the backbone that regulates both water and energy flows. Dams control the storage and release of water, which directly impacts energy generation, flood control, and downstream water supply. Power plants convert the kinetic energy of water into electricity, while transmission lines ensure the generated electricity reaches the grid and end-users. The condition and efficiency of this infrastructure determine operational reliability and long-term economic viability. Planning for upgrades or maintenance of these components is critical, as aging infrastructure can limit the ability to meet generation objectives and reliably provide grid services in the face of changing environmental conditions.

1.1.7.1 Gaps

Records describing the physical infrastructure related to hydropower (i.e., dams, reservoirs, power plants), general water regulation and conveyance, and the electricity grid have greatly improved in the level of detail provided and spatial coverage. Remaining obstacles for these data include:

- **Static nature of inventories.** Inventories describe snapshots rather than dynamic nature of infrastructure, which changes over time. For example, new development, retrofitting, decommissioning, or upgrades can impact understanding of fundamental concepts like operation status.
- **Inconsistency across different sources.** Basic parameters that are fundamental to representing water management (e.g., primary purposes for the dam or reservoir) are often inconsistent. In a comparison of datasets describing dams (with operational purposes) and power plants in the U.S., roughly 20% of dams that report hydropower have no associated power plant, while more than 70 operational power plants associated with reservoirs have no inventoried dams (Hansen & Matson, 2023).
- **Detailed descriptions of operating constraints and historical operation.** Requirements to meet social and environmental objectives such as reservoir levels to allow recreational access or provide sufficient flood control volume, or minimum flows for aquatic organisms are highly specific to individual facilities. Current inventories do not detail these types of limits or requirements, how they vary throughout the year or under different conditions.
- **Sensitivity.** Domestic security dictates that certain information is either kept at a high-level or that it may not be able to be publicly disclosed at all. In some cases, this means that detail of certain characteristics (i.e., condition of the structure, hazard potential) is limited to abstract terms.

1.1.7.2 Recommendations

Establish partnerships with entities maintaining regional and national inventories

- Increased cross-validation/quality assurance and partnership with reporting agencies and organizations or individuals that synthesize and aggregate information (e.g., the USACE that maintains the National Inventory of Dams (NID)¹²) can improve the confidence and level of detail of reported data. This is particularly important for fundamental characteristics that are tied to operations or the role of a dam in energy generation (i.e., whether operational, retired, or nonpowered).
- Key partnerships may leverage other dam-related infrastructure inventories and tools such as the Aquatic Barrier Inventory & Prioritization Tool,¹³ the American Rivers Dam Removal Database.¹⁴ At the federal level, resources from the US Fish and Wildlife Service National Fish Passage Program¹⁵ could be used to expand infrastructure resources such as the Fish Passage Webmap¹⁶. This could enhance understanding of facility attributes and capabilities as well as better track operational status of infrastructure development/decommissioning.
- Connections are also needed between structures such as dams and power plants and the electrical grid infrastructure/systems of which they are a part. Constraints on operations and markets that transcend watershed boundaries are especially important, and may be better understood by examining these perspectives at the Regional Transmission Organization (RTO) level.

Evaluate local and state-level data

- Individual state agencies are primary sources of information to the NID, but not all dams are described in this dataset. A systematic review of state-level data may help in determining a more exhaustive list of dams or structures (e.g., smaller weirs, canal drops, diversions) that are relevant to watershed or basin-scale water conveyance and storage operations. This will also help highlight further opportunities to obtain more detailed information than what is reported in the NID.
- All states but Alabama have a state dam safety office, so important information about structural condition may be obtained through these individual state partnerships.

1.1.8 Terrestrial-Aquatic Landscape and Wildlife

The landscape surrounding a reservoir and its interaction with the terrestrial-aquatic interface significantly influence hydropower operations. Factors like land use, vegetation cover, and soil characteristics affect sedimentation rates in reservoirs, water quality, and nutrient inputs, which can degrade reservoir capacity and efficiency over time. The terrestrial-aquatic interface, where land and water ecosystems meet, plays a

¹⁰ National Inventory of Dams: <https://nid.sec.usace.army.mil/>

¹¹ Aquatic Barrier Inventory and Prioritization Tool is managed by the Southeast Aquatic Resources Partnership: <https://aquaticbarriers.org/>

¹² American Rivers Dam Removal Database:

https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/American_Rivers_Dam_Removal_Database/5234068

¹³ US Fish and Wildlife Services National Fish Passage Program Resource Library:

<https://www.fws.gov/program/national-fish-passage/library>

¹⁴ ORNL's Hydropower Fish Passage Webmap: <https://www.ornl.gov/project/quantifying-national-fish-passage-data/webmap>

key role in maintaining biodiversity, controlling erosion, and managing water quality. Hydropower operators must consider these environmental factors, as changes to the landscape—such as deforestation or urban development—can alter inflow characteristics, sediment transport, and the health of aquatic ecosystems, which in turn affect both short-term and long-term operations.

1.1.8.1 Gaps

- **Low resolution of land-use data.** The USGS National Land Cover Dataset (NLCD) is a 30-meter gridded dataset based on satellite imagery. Due to changing satellites, assessment techniques, and long periods between estimates (5 years), systematic characterization of land-use changes through time has been difficult.
- **Limited quantitative detail on habitat.** Several datasets and tools provide spatial coverage of habitats that are important to fish and other aquatic organisms (e.g., NOAA’s [Essential Fish Habitat mapper](#), the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service’s [Environmental Conservation Online System](#) for threatened and endangered fish species, and the NatureServe [Explorer](#)). The level of detail and consistency varies across descriptions of fish habitat from different sources. Additionally, associated habitat information, such as current condition or quality of the habitat and the minimum streamflow requirements needed to support ecosystem functions, is also critical to comprehensively describe throughout a watershed or basin.
- **Lack of near-shore bathymetry data.** There are no national datasets for littoral zone bathymetry in large inland waterbodies, but remote sensing algorithms for coastal bathymetry could potentially be applied to estimate near shore bathymetry in hydropower reservoirs.

1.1.8.2 Emerging Solutions

Products such as the Land Change Monitoring, Assessment, and Projection ([LCMAP](#)) that are leveraged in the USGS’ Land Cover Next project provide annual snapshots of land use, beginning in 1985 through 2023 (with planned updates on an annual basis). This new product includes a land cover change index that may be helpful for calculating land-use changes associated with new development, energy infrastructure transmission lines, etc.

1.1.8.3 Recommendations

Improve detail and coverage of aquatic and terrestrial species

- Expanding coverage of species presence, population characteristics, and measures of biodiversity should extend beyond fish. Especially as techniques such as eDNA are further developed, large-scale deployment and testing can be used to assess current conditions and provide higher frequency updates to help support accurate mapping of habitat and biodiversity.
- Stakeholder mapping of local experts and agencies with regulatory or decisional authority may help in filling knowledge gaps and prioritizing species on which to focus data collection efforts.

Establish partnerships with groups that have expertise on local wildlife

- A large variety of aquatic and terrestrial species utilize reservoirs and the surrounding environments (e.g., riparian zones). Partnering with local groups and agencies may help identify species presence/absence, including for species of concern (endangered, threatened, invasive, etc.) or interest (recreational fisheries, birding, etc.).

Evaluate approaches to near-shore bathymetry mapping

- Near-shore bathymetry, in combination with reservoir level fluctuations, is an important driver of ecosystem function in the terrestrial-aquatic interface around reservoirs. There are both airborne and satellite imagery available at multiple time steps that could be used to estimate bathymetry through remote sensing imagery analysis.

1.1.9 Water Rights and Governance

Hydropower operations and planning decisions are inherently integrated with legal and political systems that govern water use for irrigation, municipal supply, flood control, and recreation. Water rights and water allocation mechanisms vary by region and jurisdiction. In the Western U.S., prior appropriation systems are used to determine allocation of water rights among various stakeholders, while other regions of the U.S. are governed by riparian rights. Some states use a hybrid of prior appropriation and riparian rights. State governments and hydrologic-basin agreements are used to manage and coordinate among the different beneficial uses that may intersect with hydropower systems. Information detailing priorities and beneficial use is the responsibility of individual states to collect and update. Each state handles information collection differently; for example, in Idaho, water rights are tracked and maintained by the Department of Water Resources, while in Wyoming, water rights information is collected and managed by the State Engineer's Office.

Another aspect of water governance is environmental regulation. Compliance with environmental regulations is often an important consideration for hydropower project licensing and is critical for meeting certification requirements such as from the Low Impact Hydropower Institute ([LIHI](#)). These regulations may be determined at the national scale through agencies such as the EPA or at the local or state level (e.g., water quality targets and standards set by site-specific assessments such as Total Maximum Daily Load [TMDL] or state environmental limits).

Critical to hydropower are licensing and permitting processes, which require input and regulatory approvals from federal, state, and local agencies responsible for water, energy, environmental, and land-

use management. Compliance with licensing conditions, environmental-impact assessments, consultation with affected stakeholders, and consideration of alternative project designs and operating strategies are integral to securing permits and maintaining licenses for hydropower projects.

1.1.9.1 Gaps

- **Complex data requirements.** To represent water use, governance, and rights, there are a variety of data types, which can add to complexity of understanding or working with this information. Some of these are spatially oriented (e.g., locations of diversions, service districts). Other data describe volume of use over time (i.e., time-series data).
- **Disparities between states and capacity to share information.** Each state has their own system and protocols for sharing information about data use. This can represent a procedural equity barrier when there are barriers to accessing information (even if it is publicly available, if it is not easy to find and use; this can pose a significant challenge to those who would otherwise benefit from it).
- **Considering the value of water to various communities.** The value of water is not only quantified in terms of revenue generated from those who are using it. Some values, especially those tied to cultural heritage, spiritual practices, or those that are non-monetary in nature pose a significant challenge to comparing alternatives or different locations where value systems vary.

1.1.9.2 Emerging Solutions

Data describing locations and key characteristics related to beneficial use, water infrastructure owners, and water sources have been harmonized and disseminated through the Western States Water Data Exchange (WaDE) Program's Western States Water Data Access and Analysis Tool ([WestDAAT](#)). This information is critical for water balance and water budgeting, as well as facilitating transboundary (whether spanning states, watershed boundaries, or simply multiple water users) water governance. Several individual states also provide sophisticated state-level data regarding water rights (e.g., California's [Electronic Water Rights Information Management System \(eWRIMS\) Database](#)); however, inconsistencies pose a challenge to working across multiple states.

1.1.9.3 Recommendations

Link governance data to infrastructure and project boundaries

- Current infrastructure inventories of either power plants or dams focus on ownership and regulatory jurisdiction of the structure and energy generation. However, there are no links established to records of authorities and rights holders.
- Detailing water rights in terms of hydropower projects can help address barriers to understanding current systems that govern the allocation of water. Lowering the bar to access the legal status and contacts for water governance may facilitate greater participation from the public in the decision making process for long-term planning for water systems.

Describe how water is used and its value to users

- While not all beneficial uses and value derived from water can be quantified in convenient terms, there may be new ways of document the specific ways in which water is being used or that it provides benefits to individuals and rights-holders.
- Both monetary and non-monetary metrics are useful when quantifying benefits; however some descriptions of the benefits may not have simple translations into numerical terms. Other metrics and mediums for summarizing the value water provides for those who hold rights for it or who benefit from its use.

1.2 DATA MANAGEMENT/INFORMATICS

Effective data management is essential for making informed hydropower decisions. The integration of diverse data sources, including climate forecasts, infrastructure performance, and ecological indicators, supports comprehensive decision-making and enhances the ability to respond to both immediate operational demands and long-term strategic planning. High-quality data management systems are indispensable for optimizing performance, minimizing environmental impacts, and improving the sustainability of hydropower projects. This section presents the current state, challenges, and recommendations for data standards, data processing and workflows, and databases and data-sharing platforms.

1.2.1 Data standards

Data standards are necessary for ensuring that data from various sources are compatible, reliable, and easy to integrate. All of these qualities are important for facilitating seamless information flows between monitoring, analysis, and decision-making processes that may be implemented by multiple organizations within a given watershed. Different categories of data standards are summarized in Figure 3.

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Figure 3. Broad categories of data standards, what these standards cover, and examples where standards have been implemented.

1.2.1.1 Gaps

- **Diversity of data types and existing standards.** Watershed and hydropower management involve a wide array of data types, each subject to different standards based on the data's origin, purpose, and intended use. Each category often follows distinct standards, making universal standardization challenging. The existence of multiple standards complicates the process of integrating and automating data flows across systems and creates the problem of deciding which standards to choose. Current practices and capabilities are for a given organization to establish and conform to its own consistent standard; for example, the USGS [NWIS portal](#) provides consistent data for its surface and groundwater observation networks, and the USBR Reclamation Information Sharing Environment ([RISE](#)) provides a consistent metadata and data format for data shared by USBR staff and monitoring systems. In many cases, there are multiple authorities who approve standards.¹⁸
- **Costs of standardization.** Adapting existing data systems to comply with new or unified data standards involves significant costs. These costs include the technical development required to

¹⁵ The Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) specifies requirements and recommendations that help individuals provide their geospatial data on the web (through Application Programming Interfaces or APIs) and ensure that their data can be integrated with any other type of information (i.e., beyond geospatial data). API Building Blocks website: <https://ogcapi.ogc.org/>

¹⁶ The Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science (CUAHSI) outlines a family of web services and a Markup Language that support information transfer from databases or data servers to personal user computers. WaterOneFlow and WaterML website: <https://his.cuahsi.org/wofws.html>

¹⁷ Environment Information Exchange Networks (EN) are used by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to facilitate transfer of information between different data owners (e.g., state agencies, tribes) and data users. Overview website of EPA's ENs: <https://www.epa.gov/exchangenetwork/learn-about-environmental-information-exchange-network>

¹⁸ Several authorities who produce and approve standards for the USGS, and the choice of standard may be determined by the science area. Examples of organizations include the [International Organization for Standardization \(ISO\)](#), [Open Geospatial Consortium](#), and the [Federal Geographic Data Committee \(FGDC\)](#)

map existing data to new standards and the ongoing maintenance to support these standards. The financial burden can be prohibitive, especially for smaller organizations or projects with limited budgets. Additionally, the process of mapping existing data to new standards requires substantial time and expertise, which may divert resources from other critical areas of watershed management.

- **Proprietary standards.** Many commercial off-the-shelf water data management software solutions come with built-in proprietary standards. These standards are often designed to ensure customer lock-in and may not be compatible with other systems or open standards. Proprietary standards can stifle innovation and interoperability in watershed management. It limits the ability of organizations to integrate diverse data systems or switch to new software that might offer better functionality or efficiency.

1.2.1.2 Recommendations

Require and support development of data management plans (DMPs)

- DMPs are designed at the outset of data collection or creation and help ensure that there is a path for applying standards which ensures interoperability.
- Key parts of DMPs include identifying persistent identifiers for features that can be used to link related datasets together. For example, a dataset describing hydropower facilities should reference and use the IDs from the dam, power plant, or hydrography datasets. Additionally, DMPs should include procedures that ensure longevity of data products, including funding for maintenance and updates to data products and tools after the end of a project.

Encourage engagement and collaboration between data collection entities

- Dialogue among stakeholders, including government agencies, private companies, and academic institutions can foster the adoption of open and interoperable standards. The Open Geospatial Consortium and the Internet of Water Coalition provide venues for such conversations.

Provide technical support to hydropower stakeholders for implementing standards

- Funding opportunities and technical assistance to organizations transitioning to unified data standards. This support could include grants, subsidies, and access to expert consultations.

Encourage industry adoption of Open Standards

- Open standards promote greater transparency, compatibility, and flexibility, allowing for broader participation and innovation.
- Support may come through training or technical assistance, particularly among private hydropower owners or those without sophisticated data engineering experts and are likely to be disconnected from coordinated and formalized data collection and management practices.

Create a map of different standards used in practice

- Work with data producers from across different sectors to describe the variety of standards currently in use, which entities use these standards, and how these standards for information can be related or understood in relation to standards used by others or for other types of data.
- This exercise will help identify the need for developing techniques to translate or harmonize information that uses different standards.

1.2.2 Data processing and workflows

Data processing and workflows play a critical role in the management of hydropower and other water systems at the watershed scale. These systems rely on accurate, timely, and efficient data analysis to optimize water use, balance competing demands, and ensure ecological health objectives are met. A 2020 whitepaper on the State of Data Science (not specific to hydropower or the field of hydroinformatics) reported that roughly 45% of data scientists' time is spent preparing data for other tasks (i.e., visualization, modeling, analysis) (Anaconda, 2020). Modifying data formats, providing sufficient metadata that describes data characteristics, dealing with missing and erroneous data, and creating crosswalks between datasets with different standards are all critical steps that enable information from different sources to move along the data-to-decision pipeline.

1.2.2.1 Gaps

- **“Last mile” for watershed data.** One of the most common challenges voiced across different disciplines and roles is the need for improved post-processing and data preparation workflows. The complexity of social, hydrologic, climatological, environmental, and infrastructural data and the need to translate or package it into usable forms is analogous to the “last mile” concept applied to package delivery for major online retailers. Major infrastructure and systems such as warehouses and fleets of semi-trucks and interstate highways are key for moving items from one location towards a given recipient, however, there is a different set of systems (e.g., the US postal system, smaller residential roads, etc.) required to get the package to its final destination. Applying this analogy to watershed-related data, there are often several systems and platforms involved in formatting, uploading, and storing information so users can access it, but then an entirely different set of systems are needed for visualizing, downloading, and processing information. Even if data are important for driving models and planning/operational decisions, barriers such as inconvenient formats, insufficient resolutions and significant post-processing steps can hinder adoption by users.
- **Working with data that is qualitative in nature.** Some aspects of human-water/energy system interactions such as perceptions or attitudes towards decisions and technologies are often collected through surveys or documented in narratives gathered through archival research (i.e., review of documents, images, and recordings). Typically, these data are highly qualitative and different from most watershed data (e.g., environmental, hydrological, operational), which poses a challenge for integrating it into models or analyses that typically require quantitative information.

1.2.2.2 Emerging Solutions

Recent efforts to facilitate setup and integration of data and hydrologic models have resulted in the ongoing updates to [Watershed Workflow](#). Suites of tools can help spin up a model and incorporate a wide variety of data types that are used to represent different watershed components or drive certain processes. This helps reduce the burden of individuals to bring together diverse data for inputs and assists in the process of documenting model formulation, which ensures that models can be more easily understood and reproduced by others (Coon & Shuai, 2022). Beyond hydrology, workflow management software has been recognized for its potential to 1) reduce computational burdens in ecological and other areas by eliminating the need to re-process inputs or repeat steps, 2) enable more frequent and efficient data updates, and 3) harmonizing information from multiple sources (Brousil et al., 2023).

1.2.2.3 Recommendations:

Develop workflows to facilitate data use

- Substantial time is spent in cleaning and preparing data from the raw form (e.g., generated from a sensing instrument, output from a model). Reducing the repetitive nature of cleaning/formatting data will increase efficiency and adoption of information into models and decision making.

Explore generative AI for data processing workflows

- Generative AI and foundation models hold promise for streamlining data workflows. Through collaborations with organizations like NASA, NEON, and USGS, generative AI may assist in data catalog searching, data pre-processing, cleaning, visualization, and storytelling. This can improve efficiency and facilitate better communication of complex data insights to stakeholders.

Apply coding techniques to translate qualitative information

- In preparation of this roadmap, qualitative responses were recorded and then translated to quantitative values through deductive coding exercises²¹. This was particularly helpful in determining the prevalence of an issue among stakeholders, as well as being able to relate topics to each other. This also applies to transforming feedback into actionable information. Feedback may come through workshops or demos, or online forms where users can provide comment on data or tools.

For example, each question about gaps in the data-to-decision pipeline elicited multiple responses from different stakeholders. We assigned a series of identifiers so all responses related to the same sector shared one identifier (e.g., all climate related responses are coded "2" and all environment related responses are coded "3"). Then another identifier was used to describe the topic or sentiment (e.g., responses about remote sensing of climate variables may be coded "2.1" while remote sensing of environmental variables may be coded "3.1").

1.2.3 Databases and data-sharing platforms

Managing water resources effectively requires robust data-sharing platforms that aggregate and analyze diverse datasets. Databases that integrate real-time hydrologic data (e.g., streamflow, precipitation, groundwater levels), environmental data (e.g., water quality, biodiversity metrics), climate projections (e.g., temperature trends, extreme weather patterns), infrastructure records

¹⁹ Deductive coding refers to using vocabulary set by the researcher, rather than using phrases or terms directly from participants (Skjott Linneberg & Korsgaard, 2019). Pre-defined terminology used to code information can help simplify and relate input to known concepts. For example, codes used to aggregate information from various engagement efforts in this study were based on categories of common hydropower-related data types and known steps within the flow of information from data-to-decision which were outlined from the onset of the roadmapping exercise.

(e.g., dam operations, water conveyance systems), and social data (e.g., community water use patterns, economic impacts) are often used to tackle large-scale systems (i.e., the watershed scale). Storage, organization, and maintenance of data can look different depending on the type and entity responsible for it, ranging from centralized government-managed repositories to decentralized, open-access platforms that facilitate collaboration between agencies, researchers, and local stakeholders.

Data sharing is crucial for watershed-scale water management and hydropower operations because it enables coordinated decision-making across multiple stakeholders, improves resource efficiency, and enhances the ability to respond to environmental and climatic variability.

1.2.3.1 Gaps

- **Data discovery for users.** Many researchers and decision makers indicated that they would like the ability to go to any point in a watershed or select a waterbody and know about every single data collection effort. The discoverability of information is a huge burden that requires familiarity with multiple platforms and data providers. As one participant put it, “you cannot use something you do not know about.”
- **Trust and security concerns.** Some data providers may be hesitant to share certain information; for example, where there are domestic security/safety concerns or where there is uncertainty in how data could be interpreted. Robust security of data is necessary to encourage trust in the data sharing/integrity process.
- **Specialized skills and cost to maintain data-management software.** Many entities with missions to address scientific questions do not have sustained, direct support from personnel who are trained in database architecture, querying, and long-term management of robust data-management software.

1.2.3.2 Emerging Solutions

Several agencies have made significant advancements towards consistency and collaboration in sharing watershed data. Notable examples include:

- The Water Quality Portal (WQP) managed jointly by the USGS and the National Water Quality Monitoring Council: <https://www.waterqualitydata.us>. The WQP integrates data from USGS, EPA, and more than 400 federal and state agencies, tribal, and local watershed organizations. The EPA [Water Quality Exchange](#) allows flexibility for users to upload data and information can be shared via spreadsheets or through custom submission applications using a structured WQX XML schema and an EPA Exchange Network Nodes or Node Client.
- The Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science (CUAHSI) [HydroShare](#), which facilitates the sharing water data, models, and code. HydroShare is primarily used by research organizations and universities, and the extent/applications vary significantly.
- The [WestDAAT](#) tool, developed by the Western States Water Council is an outcome of years-long coordination between state agencies in 18 western US states. This data sharing portal reduces the burden on an individual to retrieve data from multiple formats and agencies, which is particularly useful when tackling challenges in large interstate basins such as the Upper and Lower Colorado River Basins.
- [Geoconnex](#), a platform developed by the Internet of Water, harvests metadata for connecting water data from different data providers and uses persistent identifiers and common water-data standards to connect information across organizations.
- [HyRiver](#), is a python wrapper that facilitates retrieval of geospatial/temporal data from a variety of web services and commonly used datasets in the U.S.

1.2.3.3 Recommendations

Develop guidance for data management plans and management protocols

- Data producers are rarely directly responsible for managing repositories and data-sharing platforms. However, as they move from sharing information via project-specific websites or generic repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare, etc.), researchers can ensure their data follows FAIR principles (i.e., is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This will not only increase efficiencies in science and applications, but it will also help increasing participation and adoption of data among groups that have historically not had access or awareness of certain data.

Support crosswalking efforts

- Crosswalking efforts involve identifying the links between infrastructure and spatial or hydrographic data (e.g., which identifiers should be used, how many unique matches between two datasets are acceptable?). These crosswalks will allow better updates and coordination of information provided by different data and data sources, such as barrier removal datasets (like SARP), recreational infrastructure, and river protection data (e.g., National Rivers Inventory).

1.3 MODELING AND ANALYTICS

Because of the complexity of watershed systems and their management structure, some level of modeling and analysis is needed to make operational decisions. As such, these decision tools represent a critical link in the data-to-decision pipeline. In this context, a wide range of tools are available to enhance watershed intelligence. Considered here are tools ranging from water availability forecasting to water and environmental management.

1.3.1 Water Availability Forecasting

Efficient hydropower scheduling often depends on the operator’s ability to predict water inflow in a timely manner that enables optimal response or action. Traditionally, this forecasting has relied on established hydrological models like the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) or the Variable Infiltration Capacity (VIC) model. Many hydrologic models exist, with different functionalities and scopes (Keller et al., 2023). However, model accuracy can be limited by data availability and their ability to capture the complex interplay of factors within a watershed and river basin. Emerging on the horizon is the promising potential of data-driven and physics-informed machine learning (ML) as an alternative to these process-based models. By analyzing vast datasets and incorporating diverse sources like weather forecasts, satellite imagery, and sensor data, ML models can learn complex, non-linear relationships that might escape traditional methods, often leading to superior forecasts (NHA, 2022).

1.3.1.1 Gaps

While more accurate forecasts can help operators derive greater value from existing hydropower assets, there are several areas of critical need:

- **Ability to communicate information about how a forecasting system works.** AI/ML models are often referred to as “black boxes,” using inputs and providing outputs, but not describing the

relationships or connections between components of the physical system they are representing. This is particularly challenging for forecasting, which may have different implications for different water management purposes. Methodologies are needed to both leverage AI/ML in forecasts and be able to explain their workings and performance in a way that gives confidence to potential users and those affected by forecast-informed, water-management decisions.

- **Integrating upstream and downstream water regulation and management.** Release data from dams are often not readily available, creating a challenge to accurate inflow forecasting at downstream dams. The accuracy of any hydrologic-forecasting model relies heavily on the quality and quantity of such available data. Gaps or inconsistencies in data can lead to unreliable forecasts.
- **High computational cost and complexity.** Ensemble forecasting involves running multiple simulations with slightly different initial conditions or model configurations to account for uncertainty in inflow predictions. Ensemble forecasts provide a range of possible outcomes and associated probabilities, enabling better decision-making under uncertainty. However, running such an ensemble of complex ML models can require significant computational resources, which may pose a challenge for smaller hydropower plants. Furthermore, the translation of forecasts into decisions often requires computationally heavy optimization models. Several challenges in this area remain unsolved, including development of practical techniques that correctly ingest the probabilistic information contained in a forecast ensemble, and consideration of two-way feedback between hydropower generation (determined by a river-operations model) and electricity prices (determined by power-grid models). This type of complex representation requires technical skills and computational infrastructure unavailable to many operators.
- **Engagement across hydropower industry, watershed stakeholders, and researchers:** Engagement is the key to ensuring that advanced forecasting and management tools for hydropower are adopted and used effectively. Without clear communication of their value, alignment with operator workflows, and genuine buy-in, even the most sophisticated technologies will remain underutilized. Increasing trust in and adoption of new modeling technologies requires long-term support (i.e., personnel and funding) to sustain engagement throughout co-design, training, and implementation/feedback stages.

1.3.1.2 Emerging Solutions

The USACE has prioritized the use of forecasts in reservoir operations, as is evident in the Forecast-Informed Reservoir Operations (FIRO) initiative. This research program integrates atmospheric science, hydrology, and watershed monitoring using AI/ML to develop advanced forecasting models. Additionally, the National Weather Service produces streamflow forecasts through regional River Forecast Centers. This forecast data is crucial for both operational decision-making and emergency response during flood events.

The National Water Model is supported by the National Weather Service Office of Water Prediction. It provides short-range (18 hour), mid-range (10 day), and long-range (30 day) forecasts for streamflow and short-to-medium range forecasts for total water level based on an ensemble of weather forecasts. Given differences in model performance across the continental U.S., Alaska, Hawaii, and Puerto Rico, a more recent effort for the Next Generation of the National Water Model (NextGen) establishes unifying standards to create a structure for linking various physical process models. This allows flexible interchanging and comparison of models that operate from a consistent set of inputs while being compatible with different gridding and time stepping. The framework “takes a data centric approach, organizing the data first and mapping appropriate [modeling] solutions to the existing data.”²⁰ The

²⁰ NextGen Framework: <https://noaa-owp.github.io/ngen/index.html>

NextGen framework was first released in 2021, and is currently supported by community development through the National Weather Service and the Cooperative Institute for Research to Operations in Hydrology (CIROH).

Physics-informed ML offers a powerful hybrid approach by combining established strengths of traditional hydrological models with the data-driven prowess of machine learning. This synergy has the potential to unlock a new level of forecast accuracy for hydropower operations. These techniques improve accuracy and reliability. For example, combining statistical models with physical models can capture both the statistical patterns in historical data and the physical processes governing inflow generation. Powerful ML models may not always provide a clear understanding of the underlying physical processes influencing inflow, limiting their interpretability and making it difficult to adapt to unforeseen changes. Development of interpretable AI/ML models that quantify importance of different variables may overcome this limitation and help identify causal relationships (Hong et al., 2025).

1.3.1.3 Recommendations

Identify the most critical data required for training forecast models

- To effectively produce forecasting models, it is important to eliminate unnecessary input data requirements. Sensitivity testing can help determine which parameters are the highest priority for training models that perform well under a variety of conditions. For example, some parameters and resolutions may be more important for representing streamflow during different seasons or after particular extreme events like droughts, wildfires, or flooding. Ultimately, it is critical to determine which data features within the hydropower energy production process are most valuable for building accurate forecasting models in diverse and dynamic watersheds.

Better represent decisions, behavior, and system feedbacks

- Upstream and downstream coordination of reservoir releases and diversions: Real-time data assimilation techniques need to integrate observed data with model predictions to update forecasts as new data become available. This will improve forecast accuracy by continuously adjusting model parameters based on observed conditions.
- Human-watershed interactions and dynamics: Forecasts are typically developed based on representations of physical processes; however, dynamic human-watershed interactions (considering both global and local effects) could also shape forecasts and projections. Better incorporation of behavior and data that describe human impacts will improve accuracy of forecasts in heavily developed watersheds.
- Electricity load and markets: In parallel with water availability forecasting is the need to anticipate and respond to changes from local off-takers and pricing structures. Dynamics of regulated water systems need to account for potential variability in these systems to efficiently schedule hydropower operations.

Contribute to NextGen development

- Given the complex nature of hydropower-regulated watersheds, there is particular need for experts in hydropower and reservoir operations to test and further develop models that fit well within the National Water Model NextGen framework.

Build on FIRO efforts by improving accuracy and demonstrating benefits

- Increase accuracy of forecasts over longer terms and more extreme conditions, which may lead to increased adoption of forecasts by hydropower operators.
- Demonstration of the benefits that forecasts can provide need to be shown across a variety of operations and decisions. Specifically for hydropower, these benefits may focus on how improved scheduling for reservoir releases enables optimized power generation and improved ability to meet various operational objectives.

1.3.2 Water Resources Management and Long-term Planning

Water resources management modeling serves numerous functions, including supporting planning decisions, evaluating uncertainties (e.g., alternative water demands or climate conditions), and generating medium- and long-term operating decisions through optimization and multi-objective assessments of systems. By considering perturbations of water usage, management and planning models can be used to address challenges facing integrated, multi-sectoral water resources systems (i.e., spanning residential, industrial, and agricultural water uses as well as social and environmental systems). In some cases, models can facilitate difficult conversations between competing interests, providing a basis for parties to be aware of and influence model inputs, assumptions, and scenarios. Some watershed models are regularly used to aid in regulatory compliance and policy development such as TMDLs or flood control plans.

1.3.2.1 Gaps

- **Sufficient representation and participation in integrated systems.** Dynamic, user-centered models integrating cross-sector inputs, such as energy and agriculture, ensure adaptability and real-time responsiveness. Too often, models are not developed in a transparent, collaborative manner that makes the modeling and decision-analysis process inclusive of relevant parties and actionable for all stakeholders.
- **Integration of ground and surface water interactions.** The regulatory context for considering both surface and sub-surface water availability and quality is crucial for measuring and managing water resources. However, development of models by different agencies has been relatively fragmented, which exacerbates this issue and leads to redundancies and poor representation of these interactions.
- **Building trust in AI/ML models among stakeholders.** There are several significant hurdles to the adoption and trust of AI/ML models in water management decision making processes. First, the rapid rate of AI/ML development poses a challenge to keep up with new capabilities. Depending on how data-driven models are trained, they may not be generalizable for different types of systems or conditions. Additionally, these types of models may not provide the transparency and insight into processes because of the “black box” representation of systems, as noted in Section 1.3.1.1.
- **Effective incorporation of regulatory frameworks and water users’ needs.** Representation of governance, institutional constraints, and the ability to translate resource or development policies into technical constraints requires a specialized set of skills that bridge expertise in both scientific/engineering and legal/policy disciplines. evaluate compliance and trade-offs. Engaging different communities and including tribal nations ensures values and traditional knowledge are reflected. Other opportunities include collecting data directly from water users that allows models to account for diverse needs like irrigation, recreation, and energy production. This is particularly critical for communities facing rapid changes in local water demands driven by new technologies and data centers.

1.3.2.2 Emerging Solutions

Emerging solutions to address the gaps in watershed management modeling include:

- **Ensemble based analysis:** The rich ensemble of [streamflow projections](#) produced by the SECURE Water Act Section 9505 Assessment is foundational to long-term, forward-looking assessments of water availability. A subset of Global Climate Models has been downscaled using two different approaches and used to drive two hydrological models for the CONUS. The combination of downscaling approaches and hydrologic models along with a variety of models

and future scenarios helps those interested in streamflow projections to factor in different sources of uncertainty.

Ensemble ML continues to develop, working with multiple “base learning” models (either data-driven or physics-informed). Though a variety of techniques have been used to aggregate the ensemble of learning models, advances in boosting methods have led to greater accuracy and performance for hydrologic modeling applications (Zounemat-Kermani et al., 2021).

- **Reduced-order hydropower models:** Such models utilize advanced analytics to incorporate climate-change projections, variable water-flow patterns, and changing electricity demands into future planning, demonstrating hydropower’s evolving role. They are often used to simulate large hydro-thermal power systems within a river basin, allowing for optimized water usage and power generation across the entire system.
- **Stochastic modeling and estimations:** Seasonal and annual flows within a river basin are modeled by combining periodic autoregressive and periodic autoregressive-moving average models. Such first-order autoregressive models are used to model inflow as a stochastic variable in dual dynamic programming to solve optimal medium-term scheduling in the hydropower system. Employing such stochastic modeling tools can aid in balancing hydropower generation needs with the water requirements of downstream communities and ecosystems. Additionally, agent-based modeling (human-in-the-loop) are increasingly used for social-ecological systems (Lippe et al., 2019). These types of modeling techniques may help identify connections and mitigate actions related to hydropower operations and negative social and environmental impacts such as fish passage disruptions or altered river sediment.
- **Digital twins (DTs)** implemented for water distribution systems have led to positive outcomes such as optimizing water deliveries and leak detection (Berghlund et al., 2023; Zekri et al., 2022). Department of Energy-supported efforts to establish a Digital Twin for Hydropower Systems (DTHS) platform represent a critical first step in modernizing US hydropower infrastructure and decision-making techniques. Building on initial case studies, future demonstration of DTs for hydropower should highlight the variety of ways DTs can be used to simulate and analyze system performance under various scenarios, aid evaluation of maintenance and operations alternatives, and near-term planning.

1.3.2.3 Recommendations

Integrated modeling frameworks

- Pursue development of integrated modeling frameworks. Through strategic partnerships with organizations like the USBR and the University of Colorado Boulder's Center for Advanced Decision Support for Water and Environmental Systems (CADSWES), leverage modern tools for scenario analysis and optimization.

Represent regulatory & policy constraints

- Incorporate regulatory constraints into water-resource models to assess the feasibility and impact of different management strategies within the existing legal and institutional context. Support of interdisciplinary teams is needed to bridge the varied disciplines and knowledge required.

Develop trustable, adaptable, and transferable AI/ML models

- Rigorous validation, transparent communication of model uncertainties, and engagement with stakeholders can build trust in AI/ML models and facilitate their adoption for decision-making.

Connect upstream and downstream water users' needs

- Models of hydropower and water-resource management need to evaluate how well they are meeting needs through water provision and impacts on water availability for all communities throughout a system. This can lead to better distribution of benefits and may identify previously-unknown negative impacts.

Create opportunities for collaboration, consensus-building, and evaluation of alternatives

- Significant time and effort are required to make connections between industry, researchers, and other stakeholders (see Gaps in Section 3.1.1.1). Modeling and management analyses efforts should consider these connections as integral to the process and factor in the long timelines required to build and sustain relationships.
- Models and technologies such as digital twins can be used to drive conversations about which input data, assumptions, processes, or outcomes are most important to different entities. R&D efforts should be complemented and supported by coordinated communication and outreach efforts that include conceptual mapping to identify cross-cutting systems and feedback loops, and ensure data are usable, information is conveyed in a meaningful way that has understanding and buy-in from various stakeholders.

Support capacity building for industry

- Pursue knowledge sharing and capacity building involving collaboration with federal agencies, academic institutions, and industry groups to connect modelers with dam operators and water managers, ensuring decision-makers stay updated on cutting-edge data and modeling techniques.

1.3.3 Environmental Management

Effective environmental management within hydropower-regulated watersheds is important for sustainability and healthy functioning of essential ecosystem services. It ensures the health and sustainability of the entire ecosystem, ensuring that water resources are protected and available for all living organisms. Moreover, it helps to build up resilience against extreme events and climate change, fulfills legal and ethical responsibilities, and ultimately reduces long-term costs by preventing costly remediations.

1.3.3.1 Gaps

- **Disconnect in ecology and hydrology.** Advancements in ecological monitoring/modeling can lag behind hydrological modeling. There is also often an incomplete representation of linkages between the environment and climate in models.
- **Diverse measures used in environmental protection strategies.** The most common mechanisms used to meet environmental protection objectives are measures like minimum flow, monitoring reservoir levels, etc.; while these targets and flow or water level requirements may be well-known by system operators, the measures are consistently represented across different systems and can therefore be very difficult to represent in environmental modeling at the watershed scale.
- **Absence of feedback loops between many dynamic ecosystem services.** For example, cultural systems and historical experience may influence the ability to access or use certain environmental monitoring techniques (e.g., placement of equipment or land access could be difficult without trust from landowners), which could affect how accurately issues are represented in decision making processes.
- **Understanding ecological mechanisms better.** The connections between water operations and management decisions and ecological responses must be better detailed, especially in ecologically productive and biodiverse regions. Phenomenon such as regime shifts or tipping points in ecological systems suggest that some actions and management strategies may affect an ecosystem differently depending on the status or condition of the system. In particular, whether relationships and processes are relevant under a variety of conditions is increasingly important as environmental management and restoration must also compete with changing climate conditions.
- **Challenges with existing models.** The challenges associated with environmental modeling include:
 - the high parameterization cost of process-based models
 - many models are too difficult or specialized to apply in a generalized setting, or require specialized expertise to run,
 - legacy models are no longer accessible for use (not modernized),
 - lack of trust in the input data/model outputs.

1.3.3.2 Emerging Solutions

The [Hydropower Environmental Decision Support \(EDS\) Toolkit](#) is designed to provide a consistent methodology for helping those planning new hydropower projects to identify potential environmental impacts and explore ways to avoid/mitigate those impacts. By using six categories of river function indicators (Biology & Biota, Connectivity & Fragmentation, Geomorphology, Land Cover, Water Quality, and Water Quantity) and objective, quantitative metrics for each of those indicator categories, the EDS Toolkit provides a means for summarizing environmental impacts in a systematic and transparent way. The EDS Toolkit does not model processes over the life of a hydropower development but rather aids in identifying potential impacts and providing relevant resources that can be used to facilitate discussions among stakeholders about next steps.

1.3.3.3 Recommendations

Encourage "whole systems" analysis

- As water and energy systems evolve, the dynamics of socio-technical-ecological systems are evolving as well.²³ More complete representation and assessment of interacting systems can identify parts of systems that are not meeting objectives or maximizing positive outcomes and correct or improve management actions.
- Water quality and ecological processes are often driven by a combination of climate influences and human behaviors. Improving the representation of both parts will provide better context when analyzing environmental management outcomes, which will lead to uncovering root causes and identifying actions that can effectively address environmental issues.

Increase collaboration/awareness across offices within DOE

- Models developed or used in the DOE Office of Science (Earth Systems modeling, for example) may have direct relevance to environmental processes in reservoirs or rivers. Conducting regular reviews of available models/model outputs that are applicable to various environmental applications will facilitate interoffice collaboration.

Modernize and sustain support for legacy environmental models

- Many models used to represent physical and environmental processes in reservoirs and riverine environments rely on legacy code or outdated software programs. Support for environmental model development should consider the possibility of modernizing or integrating legacy models rather than re-creating tools.

²¹ (Scoones et al., 2020) highlights the importance of evaluating different systems when assessing issues or possible sustainability solutions because the root causes and most effective solutions are not always contained neatly in one area or there are key interactions between drivers of an issue.

2. CONCLUSION

The ultimate purpose of this roadmap of recommendations is to establish a blueprint for improved watershed management, particularly in the context of hydropower operations through the lens of an Intelligent Watershed (IW). This roadmap addresses the following needs:

1. Formalize the IW concept in the context of hydropower decision-making,
2. Prioritize research and technology development goals for improving watershed intelligence, and
3. Outline opportunities for implementing IWs within the context of human-managed systems.

We first considered the individual terms *watershed* and *intelligence*. Rather than defining a watershed according to stream order or scale, a watershed was viewed as an interconnected system of physical processes, infrastructure assets, and agents (e.g., hydropower operators, water and environmental resource managers, etc.). In this context, a watershed encompasses a water system where synergies and competition exist between various agents that control the supply and use of the water. Although there is no definitive definition, an intelligent system is generally considered one that gathers, manages, analyzes, and responds to the data it collects from its surrounding environment. These concepts were merged with the purpose of an IW, that being advanced watershed management. All together an Intelligent Watershed (IW) is defined as **an advanced watershed resource management system that coordinates the actions of interdependent agents that gather, manage, analyze, and respond to information according to their unique community and stakeholder needs.**

Specifically, this roadmap identifies strategic investments that can be made to help realize Intelligent Watersheds. Priorities for research investment include improvements to current technology deployment as well as support for capacity building and interagency collaboration that span resource management/use sectors and consider both technical and human-managed solutions:

Technology Investment Opportunities: Many emerging technology solutions (e.g., new sensors/observational techniques, computational advances and AI applications, etc.) could lead to more intelligent watersheds if accompanied by greater data integration and standardization, improving data sharing/access/processing workflows, applying hybrid techniques that leverage both AI and process-based or empirical approaches, and building model-agnostic analytical frameworks.

- **Sensing Systems:** Opportunities toward improved sensing technologies were identified for measuring streamflow, climate change, snow pack, water quality, and terrestrial-aquatic dynamics. Broadly these include expanded use of remote sensing platforms, correlating remote and ground-based measurement, improving resolution of sensing equipment, and techniques to strategically site sparsely distributed measurement equipment.
- **Databases and Data Standards:** Recommendations call for broad application of standards to ensure that data from various sources are compatible, reliable, and easy to integrate. The need for shared data portals, with applicable data standards, was consistently expressed to data that follows FAIR principles (i.e., is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).
- **Modeling and Analytics:** Identified were prospects to improve forecasting, water/environmental management modeling and decision analysis. Forecasting would benefit from real time data assimilation, integration of human-watershed dynamics, and sensitivity analyses to limit parametrization. Tool integration, broader incorporation of regulatory frameworks and engagement of water users in model development were identified steps toward improved water/environmental management modeling. Decision analysis requires renewed effort toward knowledge sharing, capacity building and collaboration.

- **AI/ML:** Artificial intelligence and machine learning has the potential to significantly influence all aspects of the data-to-decision pipeline. Generative AI holds promise for streamlining data workflows such as data catalog search, data pre-processing, cleaning, visualization, and storytelling. Water resources analyses will also benefit from recent innovations in ensemble machine learning models, reduced-order hydropower models and stochastic modeling. However, rigorous validation, transparent communication of model uncertainties, and engagement with stakeholders is needed to build trust in and facilitate adoption.

Investment Opportunities in Human-Managed Aspects: Cutting across technology-oriented solutions is the need for increased coordination among water management agencies, the hydropower industry, and researchers.

- **Testbeds:** Avenues for the diffusion of new technology from research to practice are limited. While examples of practitioners participating in research projects exist there is minimal opportunity for technology transfer to occur during the limited timeframe of a standard research project. Other challenges include the lack of broad awareness of new technologies; sufficient head-to-head comparisons between new and existing technologies to build practitioner confidence; staff training and familiarity with the new technology, and funding to implement new technologies.
- **Communities of Practice (CoP).** The idea is to create a shared space that fosters enhanced communication, knowledge transfer, sharing of data/tools, expanded networking, ideation, and collaboration around a common interest. Efficacy benefits are realized when the same datasets, workflows and models are subjected to the rigors of use by different agents. Less duplication of effort frees staff time to devote to process improvement. Also of importance is the fact that decision making is based on a shared set of information and tools—everyone is working from the same set of information.
- **Funding:** The problem here is not just insufficient funding, but rather it is the funding model. Part of the problem is that funding for sampling, databases and modeling must flow through individual agencies. As priorities often differ across agencies, coordination of funding for joint ventures takes extra work. Funding is also driven by administration and agency priorities and thus is subject to change. While funds are often available to develop a new technology, database, or model, maintaining long-term support is difficult. These challenges escalate when trying to establish long-term cross agency support for coordinated data-to-decision pipelines.

The review of gaps, emerging solutions, and recommended areas of investment are aimed at **increasing watershed intelligence**, which will lead to **optimal management of multi-purpose watershed systems in a way that increasingly focuses human engagement where it returns the most benefit, thereby optimizing resource use.**

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